

EXPLORING MEDIATION IN NIGERIA: COULD THIS BE THE INNOVATION TO DISPUTE RESOLUTION THAT WE HAVE BEEN WAITING FOR?

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INTRODUCTION

Legal technicalities, stringent procedures, high costs, tardiness in dispute resolution and every other frustration that comes along with the Nigerian court system has led to the recent adoption and institutionalization of the Alternative Dispute Resolution in the country. ADR has so many legs including, conciliation, arbitration, mediation, ombudsman, mini-trials and to mention but a few and of a truth, these other methods prove to have some advantage over the court system however this paper seeks to draw the reader's attention particularly to the practice of Mediation as it tends to offer more advantages over the court system of dispute resolution and other legs of ADR.

It is worthy to note that Mediation is a major type of Alternative Dispute Resolution. Alternative Dispute Resolution (also called ADR) is basically any means of settling disputes outside of the court.

THE HISTORY AND CONCEPT OF MEDIATION IN NIGERIA

According to the Institute of Chartered Mediators and Conciliators, Mediation is a voluntary (unless ordered by the court), non-binding, private dispute resolution process in which a neutral person helps the parties try to reach a negotiated settlement. Participation in mediation is voluntary and informal, that is, parties

decide the settlement they want and can leave at any stage of the mediation. Also, mediation process is highly confidential in nature.

While it may be no news to some, it is worth noting that Nigeria's ancient dispute resolution mechanism is highly similar to our present-day mediation. In the Nigerian traditional societies (most especially amongst the Igbo people) mediation was used as a tool for preserving cultural norms and values. Mediation prevented disputes from festering, maintained peace and preserved traditional values (e.g. the elder is always right, the younger has no alternative but to accept the words of the elder) ¹When elders had dispute, mediation was the surest way to solve such dispute. Mediation was then scrapped away due to the coming of colonialism which introduced the court (adjudicatory) system.

Mediation can be said to have been formally introduced in Nigeria with the establishment of the first court connected ADR centre in Africa, the Lagos Multi Door Courthouse (LMDC) in 2002 as a public-private partnership between the High Court of Justice, Lagos State and the Negotiation and Conflict Management Group (NCMG), a non-profit private organization. The LMDC was however statutorily established in 2007²

The practice of mediation does not have a specific unifying legislation regarding its practice, however, **sections 22 and 23 of the High Court Laws of Lagos state**³ provides that civil matters and certain types of criminal matters be settled in peaceable and amicable ways. Also, **Order 18 rule 1 and 2 of the Federal High Court (Civil Procedure) Rules 2009** makes provision for parties to explore alternative ways to settle cases filed in court (this is also the position of the high

¹ Mediation (a "face saving device") - The Nigerian Perspective by A.O Rhodes-Vivour (FciArb. Chartered arbitrator, CEDR (UK) accredited mediator.)

² The growth of Mediation in Nigeria by Morenike Obi-Farinde at Mediate.com

court rules/laws of various states as there have been enactment of laws on mediation by these states that are major commercial centers such as Akwa Ibom, Rivers State, Delta State, Enugu State, Ogun State, Edo State, Kano State have, with the most significant being Lagos State)³, hence, the practice of mediation and other branches of ADR in Nigeria.

There are three types of mediation methods used in Nigeria. There are the evaluative, transformative and facilitative mediation. According to Oregon Mediation Association, a mediator who uses an evaluative approach is likely to be appreciated for his/her no-nonsense style. Evaluative mediators work quickly and efficiently to get to the point, and write up a solution. A mediator with a transformative approach is likely to be appreciated for the time and space that he/she creates for all sides to really hear and understand one another. On the other hand, transformative mediators may create more space for emotions to be expressed through the process and to help support emotional healing along with the solution. Transformative mediators are especially useful when conflicts are tied to more deeply personal issues including identities and relationships and when parties are seeking empowerment and recognition.

In between these two ends of the mediation style spectrum are facilitative mediators. This is the style of mediation that may be most familiar to people.

³ High Court Laws of Lagos State, 2015.

Facilitative mediators are appreciated for the ways they adapt based on the parties' dynamic needs. They may use techniques from both evaluative and transformative approach. Using a facilitative style, a mediator asks questions, normalizes perspectives, and validates both parties' points of view (Oregon Mediation Association)

THE PROS OF MEDIATION

One would ask the question, what really should be the essence and the effect of dispute resolution? Should the settlement of disputes only do what the name implies or should it go beyond by preserving the relationship of parties who were in dispute? Could there be a peaceful way to resolve disputes? The practice of adjudication and vehement litigation of the court system would definitely answer negatively to the above question hence the birth of mediation in Nigeria. One of the foremost qualities of mediation is that it seeks to resolve the dispute and also restore whatever goodwill that existed between the conflicting parties and this is because in this form of dispute resolution adopts a win-win strategy.

It was earlier mentioned that mediation is informal. The beauty of its informality is that it allows for a great level of flexibility. When mediation is compared to the court system and the other kinds of alternative dispute resolutions like arbitration and conciliation, it could be seen that parties to a mediation process have the freedom to choose whoever would mediate between them. The court and other ADRs (in arbitration, the arbiter cannot be chosen by parties and he acts like a judge over the matter) are structured with so many rules to follow added to the fact that parties to these cannot choose who to preside the process.

Flowing from the above paragraph, this flexibility has made parties of the mediation process in charge as the whole process would go at the pace each party is comfortable with as opposed to the compulsory service of process for appearance associated with the practice of litigation.

Further to this, mediation is cost effective and efficient. As a result of mediation being timely, it saves costs. When compared to litigation, the cost of the mediation itself, including the attorney's time to prepare and the mediator's fees, is far less than the cost of preparing a case for trial⁴ and it has been reported that mediation can last for up to a week in contrast to trials which can take years to resolve and as a result, an encouraging percentage of Nigerians have resorted into mediation.

In addition, mediation leaves parties in a pool of confidentiality. The mediator is very much obliged to never give to any person details of a mediation process and certainly, a mediation process is never tape recorded and every note taken by the mediator during the mediation process is to be put away or better still, destroyed. This has therefore afforded parties the ease of confidentiality.

THE CONS OF MEDIATION

Mediation is not without its own few downsides. One of the biggest hurdles is that mediation has a low level of public awareness, although, this is no longer a big problem as courts in Nigeria are beginning to refer thousands of cases to mediation as well as the presence of training institutions like Institute of Chartered Mediators and Conciliators.

⁴ The growth of Mediation in Nigeria by Morenike Obi-Farinde at Mediate.com

In addition, there have been questions as to the validity of the end product of a mediation session. That is, to what extent can it be said that a mediation agreement will be enforceable in Nigeria. This problem can be said to have been solved as the Nigerian courts are readily available to enforce a mediation agreement, most especially, when the mediation agreement clause provides for that as based on the contractual principle that parties are bound by the obligations imposed on themselves.

Also, it is saddening that the Nigerian legislature has not in any way thought of drafting and publishing a new law that covers the entirety and totality of mediation so as to give it a strong backing. This may be a major setback and it does not matter that the Nigerian law has recognized Alternative Dispute Resolutions in general.

Furthermore, downside or roadblock is that most Nigerians see mediation as inferior to litigation that is why a large percentage of Nigerians are unwilling to try it out, also, mediation has a limited scope as matters leading to divorce or criminal matters cannot be mediated.

These limitations however, cannot overcome to the numerous advantages associated to the practice of mediation.

CONCLUSION

This paper has been able to explore the versatility of mediation and from the foregoing, the usefulness of mediation was pin-pointed and regardless of its downsides, mediation has proved to be a solution to most of the problems associated with the Nigerian court system and other types of ADR. Mediation has begun to receive the recognition it deserves as the public have begun to take cognizance with its practice and importance so most assuredly, there would be a

demand for mediators who are ready to make use of their expertise by the requisite percentage of the public. No doubt, mediation is absolutely an innovation, thus, is a strong foundation for solving disputes in the future.

OTHER REFERENCES

- 1) Five Top Reasons to Choose Mediation Instead of Litigation by Littleton Alternative Dispute Resolution
- 2) International Comparative Legal Guide, 2023
- 3) Lexicology Library; Mediation in Nigeria